

Deliverable D6.2

Stakeholder Reference Group Setup

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1. Publishable Summary

This deliverable outlines the establishment of the Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG) for the ObsSea4Clim project. The SRG provides a structured and inclusive platform for engaging diverse stakeholders, including policymakers, intergovernmental organisations, scientific institutions, and blue economy actors, to recognise the requirements for a standardised Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), co-design Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)-based indicators, shape data collection strategies, and promote the uptake of project outputs. Through stakeholder mapping, prioritisation, and targeted engagement mechanisms, this deliverable supports the development of user-driven, policy-relevant, and more actionable ocean-climate data. The SRG will play a key role in aligning project outputs with societal and environmental needs, reinforcing Europe's leadership in the global ocean-climate science nexus.

This deliverable outlines:

- The rationale for engaging stakeholders in the ocean-climate observations and policy, including the pathways for uptake and alignment with global initiatives (*Section 2 Stakeholders Engagement and Uptake in ObsSea4Clim*);
- The establishment of the SRG, including its objectives, expected contributions, structure and membership criteria (*Sections 3.1 Purpose to 3.4 Membership*);
- The stakeholder mapping and analysis methodology, describing how key actors were identified, prioritised and invited, and the ongoing process for assuring and increasing participation (*Section 3.3 Identification and Composition of the SRG*);
- A description of the stakeholder groups involved in the SRG, including their relevance to the objectives of ObsSea4Clim and the project's links with each group (*Section 4 Stakeholder Group Descriptions*).

2. Stakeholders Engagement and Uptake in ObsSea4Clim

The ObsSea4Clim project aims to improve ocean observations for climate assessment by bringing together key international and European stakeholders. The project addresses critical gaps in ocean data and climate monitoring that are necessary through collaboration between scientific institutions, global initiatives, policymakers, and industry representatives. Given the increasing impact of climate change, the need for high-quality ocean data and the urgency of the production of “actionable” climate information, ObsSea4Clim engages with a number of stakeholders to ensure the relevance, applicability and sustainability of its outputs.

In the context of the ObsSea4Clim project, a stakeholder is any individual, group, or organisation that has an interest in or is affected by, ocean observation and climate assessment. Through the establishment of a Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG) ObsSea4Clim ensures that the project is aligned with the needs and priorities of its diverse stakeholders. The SRG engages key actors in ocean observation, data management and climate science, fostering interdisciplinary discussions and co-designing solutions that can be effectively implemented at regional and European levels.

The SRG serves as an advisory board, as a key mechanism to validate assumptions, gather real-time feedback and promote the uptake of ObsSea4Clim outputs in decision-making processes. Through continuous and iterative engagement, the SRG helps bridge the gap between scientific research and policy application, ensuring that ocean observing efforts are driven by real-world needs. In addition, the SRG plays a role in fostering collaboration with other ocean climate initiatives, thereby strengthening ObsSea4Clim's contributions to broader climate goals.

2.1 Uptake Pathways and Strategic Alignment

ObsSea4Clim's engagement strategy is designed to collect input from different stakeholder groups and **promote the uptake of its outputs through aligned, actionable, and co-developed pathways**. The Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG) will help shape and implement the project's key strategies. These strategies highlight how stakeholder engagement is not an accessory, but a core mechanism for achieving ObsSea4Clim's long-term impact.

Strategy 1. Enhancing Climate and Ocean Forecasting, Improving Access to Data, Enhancing Data Integration and Standardisation

Stakeholder feedback will inform improvements in ocean and climate data accessibility, integration, and standardisation. This includes early warning systems, open data access, and the creation of interoperable platforms.

- **Improved predictive models:** Integrating Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) into climate models allows for better forecasting of future climate conditions and ocean changes. For example, accurate sea surface temperature data can be used to predict weather patterns such as El Niño or hurricanes.
- **Early warning systems:** Using EOVs and ECVs to develop more accurate early warning systems for climate-related hazards (e.g., storm surges, heatwaves, and sea-level rise) helps communities better prepare for and respond to extreme events. These systems benefit from enhanced data from the ocean and climate monitoring framework.
- **Open data sharing:** Encouraging data sharing and open access to EOVs and ECVs will help increase the use of climate and ocean data in both research and decision-making. Providing user-friendly access through portals (e.g., the Copernicus Marine Service, or the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)) and

open data initiatives allows policymakers, researchers, and communities to use the data effectively.

- **Creating interoperable platforms:** Developing platforms that allow easy access to and sharing of climate and ocean data, especially for regions with limited infrastructure, is crucial. Interoperability across national, regional, and global databases will make it easier for users to obtain and apply the data they need.
- **Developing standardised methodologies:** One of the main challenges in monitoring EOVs and ECVs is the lack of standardised data collection methods. Improved consistency in the way data is collected, processed, and shared will ensure that it is comparable across different regions and time periods. This can be achieved by adopting best practices and standards for observations (e.g., satellite data, ocean buoys, in-situ measurements).
- **Data harmonisation:** Harmonising data formats, units, and temporal scales across various observing systems and platforms (such as satellite-based, airborne, and in-situ observations) will facilitate easier integration and use of data by different stakeholders.
- **Linking EOVs and ECVs to existing monitoring networks:** Connecting ocean and climate data with established global networks like the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) ensures that EOVs and ECVs are consistently monitored and updated.

Strategy 2. Improving Technological Innovation and Monitoring Capabilities

The SRG will help identify gaps and priorities in observational technologies, guiding investment in high-resolution, scalable tools for data collection and monitoring.

- **Advancing observation technologies:** Investing in cutting-edge technologies such as autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs), remote sensing satellites, drones, and real-time data collection sensors will improve the ability to monitor EOVs and ECVs more efficiently and comprehensively. These technologies should be affordable and scalable, especially for developing nations.

- **Enhancing data quality and resolution:** Improving the spatial and temporal resolution of EOVs and ECVs data will help refine predictions and improve the accuracy of climate and ocean models. Higher resolution data enables a more detailed understanding of regional and local changes in the ocean and climate.

Strategy 3. Strengthening Collaboration and Partnerships

Stakeholder involvement ensures cross-sector and international coordination. Additionally, engaging with industry stakeholders also opens up opportunities for co-development of technological applications.

- **International collaboration:** Encouraging cooperation between international organisations, governments, research institutions, and private sector stakeholders is essential for expanding the collection and use of EOVs and ECVs. Collaborative efforts like the IOC UNESCO and the UN Ocean Decade, GOOS, WMO, or services like the EU Copernicus Marine Service can help align goals, improve data collection, and ensure that the observations made meet global priorities.
- **Cross-sector partnerships:** Engaging different sectors (e.g., aquaculture, fisheries, ports and coastal management) in the development and use of EOVs and ECVs helps ensure that these variables meet diverse needs. Partnerships with industries that depend on ocean and climate data can lead to innovative solutions and funding for enhanced observations.

Strategy 4. Strengthening Policy Support and Frameworks

SRG members, especially those related to policy institutions, can support the integration of EOVs, ECVs and indicators into climate policy, contributing to adaptation strategies and regulatory frameworks aligned with global targets.

- **Integrating EOVs and ECVs into climate policy:** To ensure that ocean and climate data are effectively used, it is important to integrate EOVs and ECVs, and

the indicators related to them, into national and international policy frameworks. These variables and indicators should be a key part of climate action plans, adaptation strategies, and environmental regulations.

- **Aligning with global targets:** Linking the monitoring of EOVs and ECVs to global climate goals, such as the Paris Agreement or the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), can help raise their profile and ensure their relevance. For example, aligning EOVs with SDG 14 (Life Below Water) can ensure that ocean observations are prioritised in global sustainable development efforts.

Strategy 5. Supporting Sustainable Ocean and Climate Management, Supporting Local and Regional Stakeholders

Local and regional stakeholders can help tailor data to context-specific needs. This strategy emphasizes ecosystem-based management and climate resilience, especially for vulnerable coastal and island communities.

- **Ecosystem-based management:** The use of EOVs can support sustainable ocean management, particularly in the areas of fisheries, marine protected areas, and coastal zone management. By monitoring ocean health (e.g., through temperature and acidification data), policies can be developed to ensure the resilience of marine ecosystems.
- **Climate resilience:** Data from EOVs and ECVs is vital for designing climate-resilient infrastructure and communities, especially in coastal and island regions that are vulnerable to sea-level rise, storms, and changing ocean conditions.
- **Tailoring data to local needs:** Local and regional authorities can benefit from EOVs and ECVs that are tailored to their specific geographic and socio-economic contexts. Providing localised data and decision-support tools ensures that ocean and climate data is actionable at the grassroots level.

3. The ObsSea4Clim Stakeholder Reference Group Setup

3.1 Purpose

The main objectives of the SRG are to:

- Provide expert feedback on the development and prioritisation of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs);
- Support the co-design of ocean indicators and observations strategies relevant for climate adaptation and mitigation;
- Promote the uptake and integration of ObsSea4Clim outputs into policy recommendations and sectoral activities (end-users);
- Strengthen the link between science, policy and industry through mutual learning and ongoing collaboration;
- Align project outputs with European and international policy goals and initiatives;
- Validate project outputs to increase their relevance, impact, and alignment with user needs.

3.2 Benefits and Expectations

Stakeholders participating in the SRG can expect the following benefits:

- Early access to scientific results and innovations emerging from ObsSea4Clim;
- Opportunity to influence the design and standardisation of climate and ocean data products;
- Opportunity to shape future strategies for ocean-climate observing systems;

- Opportunity to help translate ocean observations into effective policy and management frameworks;
- Networking opportunities with peers across disciplines, sectors, and countries;
- Active participation in a mission to enhance climate resilience and sustainability at both local and regional scales.

Participation is voluntary. However, SRG members are expected to:

- Participate in at least one engagement activity per year (e.g., virtual meetings, workshops, or targeted consultations);
- Review and provide feedback on selected deliverables and discussion papers;
- Share their knowledge and needs in relation to climate data, ocean indicators, methodologies and observation requirements;
- Act as multipliers by disseminating relevant project results within their networks.

Engagement will take place through a mix of activities:

- Virtual meetings and thematic webinars;
- Online surveys and collaborative feedback tools;
- Invitations to in-person workshops or project events (travel support may be available);
- Invitation to collaborate in the production of project materials (e.g. policy briefs, articles, reports, etc.).

3.3 Identification and Composition of the SRG

The identification of stakeholders to be included in the ObsSea4Clim SRG began during the proposal development phase, where an initial mapping of relevant stakeholder groups was carried out to ensure early alignment with the scientific and societal goals of the project. This early identification process focused on encompassing a broad spectrum of actors engaged in ocean observation, climate science, environmental

policy, and marine-related industry. The aim was also to ensure that both the producers and users of ocean-climate data were identified. Stakeholders were initially grouped according to their area of activity and operational level (international, European, regional and local). The SRG will include actors from the following groups:

- **Intergovernmental Organisations and International Assessments** (including, climate science institutions and experts)
- **European and International Initiatives and Projects**
- **European Policymakers and Decision-makers**
- **Blue Economy Industry Representatives.**

The preliminary list of stakeholders has since been refined and expanded through a dedicated stakeholder mapping analysis (see Section 3.3.1).

Additional stakeholders may be added in the future through an open call for interest (more information in Section 3.4). The aim is to have roughly up to 30 stakeholders actively participating in the SRG over the project duration.

Stakeholder Mapping and Analysis

The stakeholder mapping has been a fundamental step in identifying key stakeholders, understanding their areas of expertise, and determining how they can effectively contribute to ObsSea4Clim. The aim of the mapping exercise was to ensure that all potential external experts, decision-makers, and end-users who may have an interest in or be impacted by the outcomes of the project were identified and engaged. By systematically mapping stakeholders, ObsSea4Clim partners could tailor engagement approaches, align expectations, and enhance collaboration across all identified stakeholders.

Stakeholder mapping started during the proposal phase and is an ongoing process. To identify, prioritise and analyse stakeholders, the following stages were performed:

Phase 1: Identify and prioritise all potential stakeholders

- Preliminary stakeholder list (proposal phase).

During the proposal phase, WP6 worked with all project partners to create an initial list of relevant individuals, organisations, companies and projects that would be important to validate assumptions early on, gather their requirements and feedback, and follow up through execution and implementation of the solutions. This list was a preliminary exercise and culminated into a mapping of stakeholders divided in the four pre-defined groups (section 3.1). Key organisations, projects and initiatives were mapped during this phase, and some of them are presented in Section 3.3.

- Kick-off-meeting, Session on “stakeholder mapping exercise”.

During the project kick-off meeting in March 2024, a dedicated WP6 hybrid session involving the project partners was held to further refine the list of stakeholders and to begin the process of classifying them based on their level of prioritisation depending on the Work Package (WP) activities. To facilitate this, partners were divided by WP and each one was assigned to an online collaborative board (FIGMA application). Each WP group undertook two tasks:

Stakeholder identification: Project partners were asked to compile a comprehensive list of stakeholders relevant to the WPs’ planned activities (Figure 1) while considering the following questions:

- What inputs/feedback do we need for developing our work?
- Who do we need to consult/engage in order to respond to our WP needs? Who are our stakeholders?
- Where are they? Do I need stakeholders to cover all the geographic areas of the project? If possible, try to specify the country or region.
- When during the lifetime of the project do we need to involve our stakeholders? At the beginning, at the end...

Fig. 2: Snapshot of activity 2 of the stakeholder mapping exercise using the FIGMA board.

- ObsSea4Clim EO/ECV related stakeholder database.

All information gathered during the kick-off meeting was compiled into a database. The **ObsSea4Clim Stakeholder Database** is a structured and dynamic repository designed to systematically manage and track stakeholder engagement throughout the project lifecycle. It follows a predefined framework to ensure that relevant information is collected and stored in a centralised manner, making it easily accessible to project partners. The database was set up by implementing the following steps and rules:

- The database was developed using an MS Office.xls file and is shared with the project partners via the +ATLANTIC MS SharePoint folder.
- The information collected in the database includes (Annex 1):
 - Stakeholder group

- Stakeholder initiative
 - Name of the representative
 - Owner of this contact for ObsSea4Clim
 - Level of operation (international, European, national)
 - Country
 - Level of stakeholder relevance by WP (essential, keep informed and not needed)
 - Comments, consents and mandate letters.
- Further categories and criteria for mapping the stakeholders can be added based on the needs of Work Packages.
 - After compiling the information in the database, Work Package leaders were asked to complete missing information on the potential stakeholders and their level of relevance for their WP, as well as to add new stakeholder representatives.
 - The stakeholder database is managed by +ATLANTIC (leader of task 6.2)
 - When collecting the information, rules and regulations for the protection of personal data (GDPR) were taken into account (for further information please consult Deliverable D7.1 Ethics Requirements)
 - The identification and mapping of potential stakeholders is an ongoing process. The stakeholder database will be continuously updated throughout the project, and partners are requested to add new entries when a new stakeholder is identified.

Phase 2: Analysis of stakeholder relevance and selection of SRG members

Following the project kick-off meeting, WP leaders were invited to review and refine the initial stakeholder list, focusing on those considered most relevant to their respective research activities, indicator development, and application areas. As of this phase, the ObsSea4Clim Stakeholder Database includes 73 identified stakeholders, categorised as follows: 36% are stakeholders from the group “European and International initiatives and projects”, 30% from “Intergovernmental Organisations and International Assessments”, 20% from “European Policymakers and Decision-makers” and the

remaining 14% are from “Blue Economy Industry”. To support strategic activities engagement, each WP conducted a relevance assessment to identify which stakeholders were considered “essential” for their specific objectives: WP2 identified 20 “essential” stakeholders, WP3 selected 24, WP4 selected 14 and WP5 selected 15 stakeholders as “essential”.

This prioritisation process enabled the development of a preliminary list of stakeholders to be formally invited to join the SRG. Based on this analysis, a total of 44 stakeholders have been selected for invitation to participate in the SRG, ensuring a balanced representation across thematic areas and stakeholder types.

In the following sections, a more detailed description of these stakeholder groups are presented, including the main organisations representing them, what their interests towards EOVs and ECVs are and how (and through which partner) ObsSea4Clim has established a link to them.

3.4 Membership

As explained in the sections above, the composition of the SRG has been shaped through a stakeholder mapping and prioritisation process carried out in close collaboration across all Work Packages. **Formal invitations** (invitation email - Annex 2) will be sent to selected stakeholders along with a **Terms of Reference** (ToR) (Annex 3) document describing the project and outlining member roles, responsibilities and benefits of membership, and an **Expression of Interest (EOI) form** (Annex 4) to be completed electronically.

In addition, to ensure an inclusive and dynamic structure, the Expression of Interest form will also be made available via the ObsSea4Clim website. This allows additional experts and organisations to self-nominate as stakeholders to join the SRG or participate in specific dialogues, ensuring the group can grow and evolve over time. This approach also ensures that the SRG remains adaptable and representative

throughout the life of the project, and is committed to collaborating on project developments and supporting the uptake of project outputs.

3.5 Compliance with Ethical Rules

In working with stakeholders, ObsSea4Clim complies with the following ethics requirements:

- **Compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):** Personal data of SRG members will be stored securely and processed only for the purposes of engagement and communication within the scope of the project.
- **Compliance with Ethics Guidelines on Working with humans:** Consent will be collected at the time of registration or invitation, and members may withdraw at any time. Detailed information is provided in Deliverable D7.1 (Ethics Requirements), its follow up versions and in the SRG Terms of Reference.

4. Stakeholder Group Descriptions

The SRG brings together a wide range of stakeholders from across the ocean-climate landscape. As noted above, these groups were identified through a structured mapping and prioritisation process to ensure broad and balanced representation. Each stakeholder group brings specific expertise, perspectives and operational needs that are essential to shaping the outputs of the project and ensuring their relevance and uptake. The following sections provide a description of each group, their interests in Essential Ocean and Climate Variables, and their connection to the ObsSea4Clim project.

4.1 Intergovernmental Organisations and International Assessments

ObsSea4Clim contributes to the work of various intergovernmental organisations and assessments, such as the **Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), World Meteorological Organisation (WMO), UNFCCC Ocean and Climate Change Dialogue, United Nations Ocean Decade Coordination Centres and Offices, Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), Med- CORDEX** among others. Outputs of ObsSea4Clim will address key knowledge gaps in ocean observing and provide an improved framework for nations' contributions to European ocean observations in support of regional and global climate assessments.

The EOVs framework is a systematic approach implemented under GOOS. These variables are critical to understand and track the health of the ocean, as well as their impact on global climate and weather systems. EOVs help to measure important ocean properties, such as temperature, salinity, sea level, and currents, as well as biological and chemical factors, like oxygen levels and chlorophyll concentration - a key feature is that such records are observable, reliable and stable over long periods of time, allowing to disclose long-term trends and monitor the physical, biogeochemical, biological and ecological aspects of the Earth System.

The GOOS expert panels identify EOVs based on their significance for climate monitoring, operational ocean services, and ocean health. The selection process also considers the feasibility of observing or deriving these variables on a global scale, evaluating them through technical, political, and economic lenses. This ensures that chosen EOVs can be measured using proven, scientifically validated methods that are practical and sustainable for long-term global observation. ObsSea4Clim is deeply aligned with the concept of Essential Variables mainly guided through work done under WP2 *EOV and ECV framework*.

Ocean indicators are based on Essential Variables, such as the EOVs, and indicators are derived from one or more of these variables. For this reason, a tailored dialogue across ObsSea4Clim facilitated by ocean indicators will allow the definition of relevant EOVs and it will contribute to the development of the associated requirements. Indicators are situated in an upper level of the so-called added value chain for ocean knowledge transfer and allow for an interlinkage between the three pillars of sustainable development, i.e., environment, society and economy (von Schuckmann et al., 2020).

The international community has established a framework for global climate indicators under World Meteorological Organisation Integrated Global Observing Systems (WIGOS) which is under GCOS (<https://gcos.wmo.int/en/global-climate-indicators>). The work in WP3 *Indicator framework* is particularly strongly aligned with this framework.

The WIGOS 2040 vision proposes a scenario of how users for observational data may evolve in the next 20 years. which is an ambitious, but technically and economically feasible, vision for an integrated observing system that will meet those requirements. The WIGOS framework supports all activities of the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) and its Members within the general areas of weather, climate, and water.

The international ocean community is also currently working on the establishment of an [international ocean indicator framework](#) under GOOS. These international standards on the definition of and criteria for ocean indicators should build the foundation across

indicator-related work in ObsSea4Clim to ensure common understanding and methodologies.

The Rolling Review of Requirements (RRR) process is defined by the Manual on the WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WMO-No. 1160, section 2.2.4 and Appendix 2.3) (WMO, 2025). The RRR process should provide a systematic and transparent process to support the high-level design and evolution of the WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WIGOS) aligned with its Vision in 2040. In the oceanic context, the WMO has started to develop the RRR framework by identifying several critical application areas suggested by the GOOS community, such as ocean forecasting, real-time monitoring, coastal forecasting, and tsunami detection.

4.1.1. Global Climate Observing System (GCOS)

The Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) is co-sponsored by the WMO, the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (IOC-UNESCO), the United Nations Environment Programme (UN Environment), and the International Science Council (ISC). GCOS regularly assesses the states of global climate observations of the atmosphere, land and ocean and produces [guidance](#) for its improvement.

GCOS has established the framework of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) covering atmospheric, oceanic and terrestrial domains, and the majority of EOVs are also ECVs (Bojinski and Richter, 2010). GCOS expert panels maintain definitions of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) required to observe Earth's changing climate systematically.

The observations supported by GCOS contribute to solving challenges in climate research and also underpin climate services and adaptation measures. GCOS “ensures the availability and quality of observations necessary to monitor, understand, and predict the global climate”¹. GCOS works towards a world where climate observations are accurate and sustained, and the access to climate data is free and open.

GCOS is organised in a [network](#) of national focal points, which liaise within the National Meteorological and Hydrological Services on GCOS data availability and quality and inform back to GCOS on current and potential problems that might impact data availability and quality.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: Staff identified in WP4 Application areas for climate EOV/ECVs of ObsSea4Clim and Sabrina Speich (ENS), co-chair of the ocean panel of GCOS.

1

<https://gcos.wmo.int/site/global-climate-observing-system-gcos#:~:text=To%20ensure%20the%20availability%20and,data%20is%20free%20and%20open.>

4.1.2. World Meteorological Organisation Integrated Global Observing Systems (WMO WIGOS)

WIGOS is a broader framework created by the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) to integrate and optimise various global observing systems. It focuses on observations related to weather, climate, water, and other environmental factors. It brings together land-based and oceanic observations from WMO Members, as well as co-sponsored and non-WMO observing systems (including regional bodies, national meteorological and hydrological services and research institutions) ensuring a comprehensive, cost-effective, and sustainable global network.

It provides a framework to help organize and connect existing data collection systems, which will still be operated by various organisations. WIGOS also helps make better use of new and existing technology to improve how data is collected. While it mainly focuses on improving the World Meteorological Organisation's systems, it also works with other systems around the world to ensure all the important local and national groups are involved in sharing and using this data.

WIGOS is enhancing our understanding of the Earth System by supporting improved [weather and climate products and services](#), and providing significantly more, improved observations. The members of WIGOS are primarily WMO Member States and territories. These members are countries and regions that belong to the WMO, which is an agency of the United Nations. In short, WIGOS brings together a wide range of organisations and countries that play a role in collecting and sharing observational data globally.

ObsSea4Clim's partnership with the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) further enhances its climate reporting and observing capabilities. ObsSea4Clim focuses on areas such as ocean warming, sea surface temperature, marine heat waves, in line with WMO's mandate on weather, climate and water-related issues. ObsSea4Clim works on refining the Rolling Review of Requirements to respond to the GOOS and GCOS implementation plans and in compliance with WIGOS, as described in [Resolution 1](#)

[\(Cg-Ext\(2021\)\)](#), WMO Unified Policy for the International Exchange of Earth System Data.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: Sabrina Speich (ENS) and Alessandra Onida (ENS).

4.1.3. Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)

GOOS (Global Ocean Observing System) efforts are directed to improving global ocean observation systems. It aims to collect data about the oceans' physical, chemical, and biological conditions to understand ocean processes and improve forecasting for climate, weather, and environmental management.

GOOS is one of the specialised observing systems that WIGOS incorporates into its broader framework. GOOS contributes oceanic data to the integrated global system managed by WIGOS, allowing both systems to work together to enhance our understanding of Earth's environment, especially when it comes to ocean-related observations. WIGOS helps ensure that GOOS data is part of the larger effort to improve global environmental monitoring.

GOOS's role with respect to EOVs includes:

1. **Coordinating Observations:** GOOS provides a framework to coordinate the global collection of data on EOVs. This involves working with various national and regional ocean observing programs to ensure the collection of consistent, high-quality data across the globe.
2. **Supporting Global Monitoring:** By organising and integrating data from different observing systems (e.g., satellite, buoys, ships), GOOS helps provide a comprehensive, long-term, and consistent view of the ocean's behavior. This is vital for understanding large-scale ocean changes and their impact on climate, weather, and ecosystems.
3. **Improving Decision-Making:** The data collected on EOVs through GOOS helps support important decision-making for policy and management related to climate change, ocean health, and natural resource management. For example, monitoring sea level rise, ocean acidity, and marine biodiversity can inform decisions about coastal protection, fisheries, and climate adaptation strategies.

The EOVs aim to move ocean observations beyond a focus on single observing systems, platforms and programs or regions towards a system that is globally connected and coordinated. **GOOS EOVs** are defined as the mindset of ocean variables that are needed to assess ocean state and variability for important global ocean phenomena and to provide essential data for applications that support societal benefit. They are derived from sustained individual measurements or combinations of measurements that can be undertaken at global scale and in a cost-effective manner.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: EuroGOOS team and specifically the Secretary General.

4.1.4. UNFCCC Ocean and Climate Change Dialogue

The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) Ocean and Climate Change Dialogue plays a significant role in highlighting the importance of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) in the context of climate change. This dialogue provides a platform for discussions and actions that integrate ocean-related observations and knowledge into global climate policies and strategies. The role of the UNFCCC Ocean and Climate Change Dialogue with respect to the EOVs is defined as follows:

1. **Raising Awareness:** The dialogue helps raise awareness about the critical role that oceans play in the global climate system. By focusing on the EOVs, the dialogue highlights the need for continuous and systematic ocean monitoring to better understand how oceans interact with the atmosphere, carbon cycles, and weather patterns.
2. **Integrating Ocean Data into Climate Policy:** The UNFCCC dialogue supports efforts to integrate ocean-based data, particularly data related to EOVs, into climate change policies and frameworks. It advocates for the use of ocean observations in climate assessments, such as those provided by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), and emphasizes the importance of EOVs in understanding the impacts of climate change on oceans.
3. **Promoting Action:** The dialogue fosters collaboration between governments, international organisations, and scientific communities to improve the monitoring of EOVs. It encourages countries to invest in and strengthen their ocean observation systems to ensure that essential data on EOVs is available to inform climate adaptation and mitigation strategies.
4. **Supporting Research and Collaboration:** Through the dialogue, the UNFCCC encourages global cooperation in ocean research. This includes collaboration on the monitoring of EOVs and the sharing of data and findings to help build a comprehensive understanding of how ocean changes, such as rising temperatures, acidification, and shifting ecosystems, influence climate dynamics.

5. **Linking Ocean Health to Climate Change:** The dialogue emphasises the direct connection between ocean health and climate change, using EOVs as key indicators. For example, ocean temperature, sea level rise, and ocean acidification (all part of the EOVs) are critical factors in understanding both the causes and impacts of climate change, especially in coastal and marine ecosystems.

In essence, the UNFCCC Ocean and Climate Change Dialogue ensures that Essential Ocean Variables are considered within the broader climate change conversation, supporting the collection and use of ocean data to inform climate policy, research, and global efforts to address climate change. ObsSea4Clim actively participates in the UNFCCC Ocean and Climate Change Dialogue for advancing ocean science and sustainability goals on a global scale, improving EOV reliability and accuracy, in line with the decision achieved at COP2 (UNFCCC, 2002): <https://unfccc.int/documents/624131>

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: The contacts will run through the national representatives of the partners contributing to COP².

² For instance the leader of the partner ENS tea and WP2 leader, Prof. Sabrina Speich, is co-chair of the ocean panel of GCOS, which is mandated by UNFCCC to develop and realise the implementation of Convention decisions. At DMI, the leader of the National Center for Climate Research department is regularly participating in COP activities in the Danish government delegations.

4.1.5. United Nations Ocean Decade Coordination Centres and Offices

The United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030), commonly known as the Ocean Decade, aims to promote a global effort to generate and use ocean science to support sustainable development. The Ocean Decade Coordination Centres (DCCs) and Offices (DCOs), such as the [Ocean Observing Decade Coordination Office](#), play a vital role in advancing this goal, particularly with respect to the monitoring and use of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).

The following outlines the role of the Ocean Decade Coordination Centres and Offices with respect to the EOVs:

1. **Facilitating Global Coordination:** The Coordination Centres and Offices help coordinate global efforts to monitor and collect data on the Essential Ocean Variables. They work with various national and regional organisations, scientific communities, and stakeholders to ensure that the observation of these key ocean variables is consistent, standardised, and aligned with global priorities.
2. **Promoting the Ocean Observing Systems:** The Ocean Decade emphasises the need for improved ocean observations to better understand the ocean's role in climate regulation, weather systems, and ecosystems. The Coordination Centres and Offices help to enhance existing ocean observing systems (such as GOOS) and facilitate new initiatives that focus on improving the monitoring and reporting of EOVs.
3. **Encouraging Data Sharing and Collaboration:** One of the main goals of the Ocean Decade is to ensure that ocean data is freely and openly accessible to all. The Coordination Centres and Offices support the sharing of data on EOVs by fostering collaboration between countries, research institutions, and ocean monitoring organisations. This open data sharing helps build a more comprehensive, global picture of ocean health and its changes over time.
4. **Supporting Research and Capacity Building:** These offices provide support for research initiatives and capacity-building activities related to ocean science and EOVs. This includes strengthening the technical and scientific capacity of

countries and institutions to monitor and analyze EOVs, especially in developing regions where ocean science and observation capabilities may be limited.

5. **Advocating for Policy Integration:** The Ocean Decade Coordination Centres and Offices also work to ensure that the monitoring of EOVs is integrated into international policy frameworks, such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Paris Agreement on climate change. By providing scientific evidence on the state of the oceans, they help influence decisions that protect the oceans and contribute to global climate change efforts.
6. **Aligning with Global Ocean Priorities:** The Ocean Decade promotes a framework for advancing key ocean priorities, including sustainable use of marine resources, protection of marine ecosystems, and climate change mitigation. EOVs are central to these efforts, as they provide essential data for understanding ocean health, predicting climate impacts, and informing conservation and management policies.

In summary, the United Nations Ocean Decade Coordination Centres and Offices play a critical role in advancing the observation and use of Essential Ocean Variables by fostering global coordination, enhancing ocean observation systems, promoting data sharing, supporting research, and integrating ocean science into policy decisions. Through these efforts, they help ensure that the monitoring of EOVs contributes to a sustainable and healthy future for the world's oceans.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: EuroGOOS is a Decade Implementing Partner.³

³ <https://oceandecade.org/decade-implementing-partners/>

4.1.6. Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP)

CMIP is a project of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) providing climate projections to understand past, present and future climate changes. CMIP and its associated data infrastructure have become essential to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and other international and national climate assessments. CMIP will benefit specifically from the assessment and evaluation of marine extreme indicators in historical and projection outputs of Earth System Models (ESM) and from the optimised parameter tuning of ESM's and reduced uncertainties in projections, also through impacts of physics on the carbon cycle modules of ESMs.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: Giulia Bonino and Simona Masina (CMCC)

4.1.7. Med-CORDEX

Med-CORDEX is a Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment. It is a framework where the research community will make use of both regional atmospheric, land surface, river and oceanic climate models and coupled regional climate system models for increasing the reliability of past and future regional climate information and understanding the processes that are responsible for the Mediterranean climate variability and trends. Med-CORDEX was born on the initiative of the Mediterranean climate research community. Med-CORDEX takes advantage of new very high-resolution Regional Climate Models (RCM, up to 10 km) and of new fully coupled Regional Climate System Models (RCSMs), coupling the various components of the regional climate.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: Giulia Bonino (CMCC)

4.2 European and International Initiatives and Projects

ObsSea4Clim works in close coordination with its sister projects **BioEcoOcean** and **BioGeoSea**, forming a 'European EOVS Network' to facilitate close communication and collaboration. In addition, ObsSea4Clim also coordinates and communicates with several other initiatives, projects, organisations, and innovation activities, including the **European Space Agency, EMODnet, Copernicus Services (e.g., C3S and Marine Service)**, as well as, EU mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" lighthouse projects, Destination Earth and the European Digital Twin of the Ocean. The main objectives to engage with these projects and initiatives are:

- Explore synergies and opportunities for exploiting project outputs
- Foster a shared understanding of how projects interconnect and influence one another
- Coordinate activities to collectively address key open science questions
- Highlight the added value of working together across initiatives

4.2.1. European Space Agency

Organisations like the European Space Agency (ESA) that provide satellite observations for ocean monitoring would benefit from high-level guidance on ensuring that their data aligns with the requirements of EOVS and ECVs. A link here can be done via the EOVS and the indicators; because satellite data will be used in line with other products (in situ, model), and new methods will be tested, intercomparing; providing new uncertainty frameworks. A case in point of engaging with ESA is the Marine Heat Waves (MHWs)-focused activities being undertaken in ObsSea4Clim. As part of this effort, links have been established with ESA projects that are part of the ESA Ocean Science Cluster, and contribute to the joint EC-ESA Earth System Science Initiative launched by ESA and the European Commission (EC) Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) - in particular, with the ESA CAREHeat project.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: Ana Patrícia Oliveira (+ATLANTIC CoLAB)

4.2.2. EMODnet Physics

In the ObsSea4Clim project, all in-situ data comes from already established workflows and networks originating from the advancements made by the GOOS, in developing operational physical oceanography capabilities. EMODnet is the European Commission program that provides access to in situ marine data and products.. EMODnet Physics, one of the seven thematic projects implementing the program, aligns with the principle to “collect once and use many times” and builds on existing infrastructures. EMODnet Physics is federated with other main European data aggregating infrastructures, namely, the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service - In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre for operational data flow, SeaDataNet and its network of National Oceanographic Data Centres for research-quality delayed mode data, the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea, the Joint Technical Commission for Oceanography and Marine Meteorology In-Situ Observations Programme Support Centre (OceanOPS), as well as other specialised databases/infrastructures that align with EMODnet [Physics] goals.

This integration ensures in-situ data is consolidated, offering a single point of access, free of charge and without restrictions, to in-situ ocean physics time-series data, vertical profiles, data products, and metadata built with common standards. More specifically, time series and datasets are made available as recorded by fixed platforms (moorings, tide gauges, HF radars, etc.), moving platforms (ARGO, Lagrangian buoys, ferryboxes, etc.), and repeated observations (CTDs, etc.). ObsSea4Clim is consuming data from these infrastructures and by consuming data is implementing gap analysis that will help discover and include more data into EMODnet [Physics] and federated infrastructures.

ObsSea4Clim will use data from EMODnet, and in particular the in situ data from the EMODnet Physics, to monitor and understand ocean phenomena essential for climate analysis and prediction. EMODnet will play a key role in implementing the RRR strategy for ocean climate observing. EMODnet is the identified European endpoint for newly

recorded in situ data and ObsSea4Clim will promote and facilitate the implementation of workflows to ensure the provision of Essential Ocean Variables and Essential Climate Variables to EMODnet. ObsSea4Clim will also recommend on how to organize new EO/ECV thematic layers under EMODnet to widen the initiative to new and more potential stakeholders and users.

The amount of new in situ data available into EMODnet [Physics] (where “new data” is not only freshly new recorded data, it’s also already recorded measurements that were not accessible and integrated yet) and the amount of updated metadata quality attached to this data will be used as key performance indicators (KPIs) for the ObsSea4Clim enabling and facilitating actions on in situ data. Moreover, ObsSea4Clim will work on recommendations on improving the completeness and quality of available metadata of the available in situ data.

Efforts will be made to facilitate seamless connections aimed to support interoperability wherever possible. The assessment of metadata completeness and quality, combined with utilising resources like the IOC-OBPS open repository and support from organisations like IEEE, will foster alignment with international standards and best practices. By collaborating with initiatives like EMODnet (European Marine Observation and Data Network), ObsSea4Clim will gain access to critical datasets and analytical tools, enriching its capacity for climate analysis and prediction.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: Antonio Novellino (ETT)

4.2.3. Copernicus Marine Service In Situ Thematic Centre (CMS INS TAC)

Data centers that store and manage ocean and climate data would benefit by receiving clear guidelines on the evolving requirements for EOVs and ECVs, ensuring their data remains relevant and valuable for global needs.

By collaborating with the Copernicus Marine Service (CMS) ObsSea4Clim will gain access to critical datasets and analytical tools, enriching its capacity for climate analysis and prediction. CMS is a parameter-oriented initiative: in the CMS In Situ Thematic Assembly Center (CMS INS TAC), the available themes cover temperature, salinity and current profiles, sea level trends, wave height and period, wind speed and direction, water turbidity (light attenuation), underwater noise, and river flow.

The amount of new in situ data available into European marine in situ data integrators and the amount of updated metadata quality attached to this data will be used as KPIs for the ObsSea4Clim enabling and facilitating actions on in situ data. EMODnet is federated with the Copernicus Marine Service - In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre for operational data flow, and this implies that CMS INS STAC is also aligned with the EMODnet for data that are fitting the Copernicus Marine Service scope. The shift towards an EOVs/ECVs-centric system will support and enable the widening of the scope and stakeholders of these European data infrastructures.

ObsSea4Clim develops new strategies through multidisciplinary collaboration to improve the transfer of ocean knowledge, with a particular focus on ocean indicators. These indicators, crucial at the interface between science and policy, have traditionally suffered from a lack of innovative dissemination tools. Given the multiple environmental stressors affecting the ocean, such as Climatic Impact Drivers (CIDs) like ocean warming, salinity changes and stratification, it is imperative to develop a comprehensive understanding of these factors. This project will analyse these CIDs in the North Atlantic and European regional seas to reveal the combined effects of long-term changes. By developing new tools to monitor these changes, ObsSea4Clim supports evidence-based decision-making and policy formulation and will develop new

products to be included under the Copernicus Marine Service - Ocean Monitoring Indicators.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: Karina von Schuckmann (MOI)

4.2.4 Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)

By collaborating with organisations such as the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), ObsSea4Clim will gain access to critical datasets and analytical tools, enriching its capacity for climate analysis and prediction.

The Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) plays a vital role in the observation, monitoring, and analysis of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) by providing high-quality, accessible climate data, integrating ocean observations into climate models, and supporting global frameworks for climate action. Through its contributions, C3S helps improve understanding of the ocean's role in climate change, supports decision-making, and contributes to global efforts to monitor and mitigate climate impacts.

The following provides an overview of the role of C3S with respect to EOVs:

1. **Providing Climate Data and Information:** The Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) provides comprehensive climate data records, including those related to ocean variables. The service collects, processes, and distributes data on EOVs such as sea surface temperature, ocean salinity, sea level, and ocean heat content. These data products are critical for monitoring long-term trends in ocean health and understanding the role of the oceans in global climate systems.
2. **Integration of Ocean Data into Climate Models:** C3S integrates EOVs into its climate models, which help forecast future climate scenarios and understand how ocean changes (such as rising sea levels or shifting currents) impact weather patterns, ecosystems, and climate. By including ocean variables in its

climate models, C3S supports the global understanding of the ocean's role in climate regulation, providing stakeholders with information for decision-making in climate adaptation and mitigation.

3. **Facilitating Data Access and Sharing:** One of the key functions of C3S is to ensure that EOVs and other climate data are accessible to scientists, policymakers, and other stakeholders. The C3S provides easy access to a wide array of ocean-related datasets, supporting international climate research and ocean monitoring initiatives. This open access helps enhance global cooperation and ensures that ocean data is widely available for research, policy-making, and planning.
4. **Supporting the Implementation of International Frameworks:** C3S plays a role in supporting the implementation of international frameworks such as the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), WMO, and the UN Climate Change Framework (UNFCCC). By contributing accurate and timely EOV data to these frameworks, C3S helps ensure that ocean data is integrated into global climate assessments and reports, such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) assessment reports.
5. **Monitoring and Reporting Ocean Change:** Through its services, C3S provides critical data on ocean changes, which are central to understanding the impacts of climate change. This includes providing information on ocean heat content, sea surface temperature, and sea level rise, which are key indicators of climate change. By tracking and reporting these EOVs, C3S helps to monitor how ocean conditions are evolving and how these changes contribute to climate variability.
6. **Contributing to Policy and Decision-Making:** The information provided by C3S on EOVs supports evidence-based decision-making at national and international levels. Policymakers rely on C3S data to assess the effects of climate change on coastal areas, fisheries, marine biodiversity, and more. C3S enables governments and organisations to develop adaptation strategies, climate action plans, and policy measures that take ocean variables into account.

7. **Capacity Building and Climate Services:** C3S helps build capacity, particularly in developing countries, by providing tools, training, and support for using ocean and climate data effectively. This is important for ensuring that stakeholders in vulnerable regions have the resources and knowledge to understand and address the impacts of changing ocean conditions on their communities and economies.
8. **Supporting Ocean Observing Networks:** C3S works closely with global ocean observing networks such as the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), contributing to the integration of EOVs into long-term monitoring systems. This collaboration ensures that EOVs are consistently observed, standardized, and shared globally to support scientific research, climate prediction, and global environmental monitoring.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: Through the DMI coordination team.

4.3 Blue Economy Industry

The Blue Economy industry plays a crucial role in the ObsSea4Clim, both as a user and contributor of ocean and climate data. Sectors such as maritime transport, fisheries, aquaculture, offshore energy, and port operations rely heavily on accurate and timely ocean information to support their operational decision-making, risk management, and long-term planning. These sectors are directly impacted by phenomena such as ocean warming, marine heatwaves, and sea-level changes, core areas addressed by ObsSea4Clim.

In addition, engaging industry stakeholders ensures that the project's outputs are tailored to real-world needs, enhancing the relevance, applicability, and uptake of ObsSea4Clim exploitable results. Blue economy actors can offer valuable insights, innovation potential, and infrastructure that contribute to the co-development and implementation of integrated ocean observing systems. ObsSea4Clim fosters this collaboration and will target engagement activities with this group, aiming to bridge the gap between science and commercial practice. Some blue economy industry important to ObsSea4Clim include:

- **Fisheries and Aquaculture associations and companies:** Private companies working in the fisheries and aquaculture sector, which depend on ocean-climate data to assess ecosystem changes, manage resources sustainably, and adapt to climate-driven environmental variability (E.g. Docapesca (PT), Fisheries Management Scotland, Federation of European Aquaculture Producers, Portuguese Aquaculture Association, National Federation of Fishermen's Organisations, etc.).
- **Port Authorities and Maritime Transport companies:** Companies operating in the maritime sector, which rely on ocean forecasting and sea-level information to support safe navigation, infrastructure planning, and operational efficiency for ports and shipping (e.g. Association of Ports of Portugal, Hellenic Marine Environment Protection Association, etc.).

- **Offshore Renewable Energy:** Private companies operating in offshore wind, wave, and tidal energy which use ocean observations and data for site selection, infrastructure resilience and daily operation, and environmental monitoring and compliance.
- **Ocean Technology Companies:** Private companies that develop ocean observing instruments and platforms (e.g., autonomous underwater vehicles, sensors, and monitoring equipment) would benefit from knowing the high-level requirements for EOVs and ECVs. This would allow them to better design and innovate technologies that meet the needs of global ocean monitoring systems.
- **Data Analytics Firms:** Companies focused on data analysis and visualisation in ocean science or climate monitoring would benefit from clarity on the evolving requirements, enabling them to develop tools that can handle the large-scale ocean and climate data.

Main contact in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: Paula Salge (+ATLANTIC CoLAB)

4.4 European Policymakers and Decision-Makers

Governments, at different levels, need to develop climate adaptation and mitigation strategies. Clear guidance on ocean monitoring and requirements would allow them to align their national policies with global ocean and climate strategies. For these efforts to be effective, governments and public institutions require access to timely, policy-relevant, and scientifically grounded information on ocean and climate dynamics. A key aim of ObsSea4Clim is to maintain a regular two-way dialogue with European policy and decision makers to ensure the research is both informed by and supports policy and monitoring needs.

This target group includes but is not limited to, relevant Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) and their assistants, EP group advisors, EC policy officers and officials, and different national agencies and institutions related to environment, climate and maritime affairs. With the European Commission Services, the activities under Horizon Europe Clusters: CL5 (Climate, Energy, Mobility), CL4 (Digital, Industry, Space) and CL6 (Food, Natural Resources, Agriculture, Environment) are relevant to ObsSea4Clim. Additionally, the Horizon Europe Missions including “Adaptation to Climate Change” and “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” will be targeted as ObsSea4Clim outputs can complement activities under these missions’ mandate.

[Main contacts in the ObsSea4Clim consortium: DMI Coordination team and EuroGOOS team](#)

5. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific objectives of the project.

#SO1	<p>To develop ocean indicators, provide improved EOV/ECVs and evolve European ocean observing</p>
<p>The Stakeholder Reference Group plays a fundamental role in supporting the collaborative development and uptake of improved EOVs, ECVs and ocean indicators by providing a structured and inclusive stakeholder engagement platform covering a number of organisations operating at international and European level.</p>	
SO2	<p>To advance the use of EOV and ECV's for improved ESM and reduced uncertainty in projections</p>
<p>The Stakeholder Reference Group can facilitate the engagement with stakeholders who both produce and use ocean-climate data and modeling outputs.</p>	
SO3	<p>To create an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs</p>
<p>The SRG ensures that the project's transition toward an EOV/ECV-centric observation framework is grounded in real-world interoperability needs. This includes alignment on data formats, access protocols, and standardisation practices that serve multiple applications, from ocean health to climate services.</p>	
SO4	<p>To develop best practices and standards for interoperable in-situ and satellite observing</p>

<p>The SRG contributes to the development and adoption of best practices and standards for interoperable in-situ and satellite observations by enabling an open dialogue between ObsSea4Clim partners and a diverse community of stakeholders.</p>	
<p>SO5</p>	<p>To place Europe in the forefront of the global coordination of the broader ocean-climate nexus</p>
<p>The SRG will facilitate inclusive dialogues with actors from initiatives such as GOOS, WMO, and the Copernicus program, and then strengthen the European capacity to influence global observing priorities.</p>	

6. References

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Annex 1. SRG Database Information

<u>Stakeholder group</u>	<u>Stakeholder initiative</u>	<u>Name of the representative</u>	<u>Email address</u>	<u>Owner of this contact for ObsSea4Clim</u>	<u>Level of operation</u>	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	<u>Consent (Y/N)</u>	<u>Mandate letter (Y/N)</u>
(dropdown list) The Stakeholders Groups defined during the proposal. They are: -Climate Ocean science - projects and initiatives - Decision Making and Blue Economy industry See AUX sheet for full description	List all organisations, groups, projects and programs.	The name of the stakeholder. The person to be contacted for ObsSea4Clim activities.	The stakeholder email address.	The ObsSea4Clim contact person who will contact or help to engage the representative.	(dropdown list) Level of operation (I= int. E= European N= national (specify which one), S= sea basin)	(dropdown list) Relevance of this stakeholder for the work packages (rate 1= Not essential; rate 2= Keep informed 3= Essential) for their involvement in the WPs work.					The consent for GDPR has been obtained.	The mandate letter appointing this person as representative of the initiative has been obtained.

Annex 2. Invitation letter

Subject: Invitation to join the ObsSea4Clim Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG)

Dear [Name],

We are pleased to invite you to become a member of the Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG) for the [ObsSea4Clim project](#), a Horizon Europe initiative aimed at enhancing ocean observation for climate assessment and policy support.

ObsSea4Clim brings together leading European institutions to co-develop improved climate indicators, refine observing system requirements, and foster the use of ocean-climate data across policy, industry, and science. The SRG will play a central role in ensuring that our project remains relevant, inclusive, and aligned with stakeholder needs.

As a member of the SRG, you will have the opportunity to:

- Contribute your expertise to shaping the direction and outputs of ObsSea4Clim;
- Access early insights from cutting-edge research and innovation activities;
- Participate in collaborative dialogues with a diverse network of peers from policy, science, and industry;
- Influence the development of practical tools and strategies for improved ocean-climate services.

We expect SRG members to participate in at least one engagement activity per year and to provide occasional feedback on selected outputs or thematic areas relevant to your expertise. You can find more details about the group's composition, purpose, benefits and expectations in the attached Terms of Reference.

To confirm your interest in joining the SRG, please complete the short registration form via our website: [\[Insert link to Expression of Interest form\]](#)

Should you have any questions, feel free to contact us at paula.salge@coabatlantic.com

We would be delighted to welcome you into the ObsSea4Clim Stakeholder Reference Group and look forward to the possibility of collaborating with you.

Warm regards,
Paula Salge

Annex 3. Terms of Reference (ToR)

ObsSea4Clim Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG)

Participant Information Sheet & Data Protection Policy

The ObsSea4Clim Project

It aims to improve ocean observations for climate assessment by bringing together key international and European stakeholders. The project will address critical gaps in ocean data and climate monitoring that are necessary through collaboration between scientific institutions, global initiatives, policymakers, and industry representatives. Given the increasing impact of climate change, the need for high-quality ocean data and the urgency of the production of “actionable” climate information, ObsSea4Clim recognises that effective stakeholder engagement and uptake are essential to ensure the relevance, applicability and sustainability of its outputs.

Participation Information Sheet

Who are the members of the SRG?

The ObsSea4Clim Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG) brings together a diverse group of experts and actors from across the ocean-climate knowledge system:

- Intergovernmental organisations and International Assessments
- European and international initiatives and projects
- European Policymakers and decision-makers
- Blue economy industry.

Participation is voluntary.

The aim of the Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG)

- Provide expert feedback on the development and prioritisation of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs);
- Support the co-design of ocean indicators and observing strategies relevant to climate adaptation and mitigation;
- Promote the uptake and integration of ObsSea4Clim outputs into policy recommendations and sectorial activities (end-users);

- Strengthen science-policy-industry connections through mutual learning and ongoing collaboration;
- Align project outputs with European and International policy goals and initiatives;
- Validate project outputs to enhance their relevance, impact, and alignment with end-user needs.

Why should you join the SRG?

- Early access to scientific results and innovations emerging from ObsSea4Clim;
- The opportunity to Influence the design and standardisation of climate and ocean data products;
- A chance to shape future strategies for ocean-climate observing systems;
- The opportunity to help translate ocean observations into effective policy and management frameworks;
- Networking opportunities with peers across disciplines, sectors, and countries;
- Active participation in a mission to increase climate resilience and sustainability at both local and regional scales.

What are we expecting you to do in this Group?

- Participate in at least one engagement activity per year (e.g., virtual meetings, workshops, or targeted consultations)
- Review and provide feedback on selected deliverables and discussion papers
- Share their knowledge and needs in relation to climate data, ocean indicators, methodologies and observation requirements
- Act as multipliers by disseminating relevant project results within their networks.

How to join?

We need you to complete the Expression of Interest form

	I have read and understood the Privacy Policy . I agree with the storage of my data for the described purpose. *
	I wish to join the ObsSea4Clim Stakeholder Reference Group, please complete the online form here. *

* = required field(s)

How can you withdraw your participation from the ObsSea4Clim SRG?

You are free to withdraw at any stage by contacting paula.salge@colabatlantic.com. +ATLANTIC CoLAB represents the point of contact for the stakeholder reference group and will handle the response and any necessary coordination with the consortium. Any information you have provided up to that point will be deleted.

Annex 4. Expression of Interest form (Eoi)

Join the ObsSea4Clim Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG)

Thank you for your interest in becoming part of the **Stakeholder Reference Group (SRG)** for the ObsSea4Clim project. The SRG is a space for open collaboration between the project team and a diverse community of stakeholders. By joining the SRG, you will have the opportunity to share your insights, help shape priorities, and contribute to making ocean and climate data more useful, accessible, and impactful for real-world decisions.

Please complete the form below to express your interest in joining the SRG.

1. Contact Information

- Full Name:
- Organisation / Affiliation:
- Position / Role:
- Email Address:
- Country:

2. Stakeholder Category (Please select all that apply)

- Intergovernmental Organisation
- International Initiative / Project
- Government (public) Agency
- Research or Academic Institution
- Blue Economy Industry (e.g., ports, fisheries, aquaculture, ocean tech)
- NGO / Civil Society
- Other (please specify): _____

3. Areas of Expertise or Interest (Please select all that apply)

- Ocean Observation & Monitoring
- Climate Indicators / EOVs / ECVs
- Data Integration & Interoperability
- Marine Policy / Governance
- Ocean-Climate Modeling
- Marine Biodiversity & Ecosystems
- Decision Support / Early Warning Systems

- Blue Economy & Innovation
- Other (please specify): _____

4. In what way would you like to engage with ObsSea4Clim?

- Attend project webinars and workshops
- Provide feedback on project deliverables and indicators
- Participate in consultation activities
- Share use cases and support data uptake
- Disseminate project results within my network
- Other (please specify): _____

5. Informed Consent

I volunteer to contribute to the activities conducted in the context of ObsSea4Clim.

- Yes
- No

I have read the [ObsSea4Clim information sheet](#).

- Yes
- No

I give my consent as framed in the [informed consent](#) document.

- Yes
- No

6. Privacy of my data

I have read and understood the [ObsSea4Clim privacy policy](#). I agree with the storage of my data for the described purposes.

- Yes
- No

I agree to receive updates and communications related to the ObsSea4Clim.

Yes

No

Submit (Button)